

Disentangling preferences for olive oil taste and healthiness. An incentivised experiment in Morocco and Tunisia

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Abstract. Olive oil is a key agri-food product in North African countries, yet local diets have been shifting towards less healthy vegetable oils, often driven by policy incentives. On the one hand, local consumers show limited awareness of the health benefits of olive oil. On the other hand, there is a scarcity of studies on consumers' preferences for this product, with existing research relying on non-incentivised methods, which are subject to hypothetical bias. We use an experimental auction with tasting and the progressive disclosure of information to comparatively assess consumers' preferences for national brands of 'extra virgin' olive oils in Tunisia and Morocco, two important producing countries of which the latter sees no peer reviewed research on this topic. The oils we consider differ in polyphenol content, which is related to bitterer taste and pungent mouthful sensation – generally disliked according to the extant literature – but also to healthiness. Along the experiment, we provide a health-focused nudge, in the form of information about the polyphenol-taste-healthiness linkage. We collect data from over 200 urban consumers in each country. We find no baseline differences in willingness-to-pay (WTP) depending on taste, polyphenol content, or local origin, which we include as an additional key attribute. However, the nudge increases WTP for bitter/pungent oils compared to sweet ones, with the impact persisting even when consumers experience the taste again. These results suggest that a simple, concise message can incentivise consumption of healthier olive oil in a developing country context. Local producers could leverage this to promote their brands, thus supporting local livelihoods and reducing dependence from imported oils.

Keywords: extra virgin olive oil; consumer preference; experimental auction; willingness to pay; health nudge; polyphenols; origin.

1. Introduction

Olives and olive oil are important agri-food products in the Mediterranean region, including in North African countries, where they contribute significantly to the livelihoods of local farmers and olive oil has been a key component of the local Mediterranean diet (Bach-Faig et al., 2011). There is a consensus in the literature that regular consumption of olive oil would generate significant health benefits for the population and should be recommended by health authorities (Vitaglione et al., 2015). Such health benefits derive primarily from olive oil's phenolic compounds (Berrougui et al., 2015; Cicerale et al., 2010; Clodoveo et al., 2022).

Nevertheless, a higher polyphenol content results in bitterer taste and more pungent mouthfeel sensation (Barbieri et al., 2015). There is compelling evidence in the literature that consumers prefer olive oils characterised by sweeter taste and low intensity of bitterness and pungency, at least in the Global

North (Delgado & Guinard, 2011; Recchia et al., 2012; Valli et al., 2014; Piochi et al., 2021). Most of the extant studies rely on sensory analysis, but Caracciolo et al. (2020) show that such preferences are reflected in a negative willingness-to-pay (WTP) for pungency. While we can assume that *ceteris paribus*, consumers would prefer healthier products (Ran et al., 2017), healthiness is not communicated by a product itself. Therefore, if consumers' choices are based exclusively on taste preferences, most of them would miss the opportunity to consume healthier olive oils, as they would opt for sweet alternatives such as refined olive oil or seed oils (Vitaglione et al., 2015).

In North Africa, olive oil faces additional challenges. For instance, Tunisia has opted for exporting most of its production (Ben-Hassine et al., 2022a), and has designed a food subsidy system also aimed at achieving this goal (Drogue et al., 2019). Consequently, Tunisian consumers have switched towards imported vegetable oils (Drogue et al., 2019), as shown by the low incidence of olive oil on internal oil consumption, 7.4kg out of 25.7kg in 2015 (Tunisian National Institute of Statistics, 2015). At the same time, Morocco has been moving away from the Mediterranean diet, with its strong reliance on olive oil consumption (El Rhazi et al., 2012). Therefore, in both countries there is a need to promote consumption of local olive oil for improving the health of the population at large as well as supporting local farmers' livelihoods and reducing dependence on imports (Drogue et al., 2019). Noteworthy, the literature and anecdotal evidence suggest that consumers tend to prefer national and local oils (Dekhili et al., 2011).

We can hypothesise that average consumers who express preference for sweeter oils are unaware of the relationship between bitterness, pungency, and the richness in phenolic compounds, which are in turn responsible for some of the health benefits of olive oil (Barbieri et al., 2015). Labelling is a key strategy to signal a product's non-visible attributes like health benefits, particularly when there is a mismatch with consumers' sensory perception. However, labels are often characterised by an excessively technical terminology, which is not easily understood by average consumers. For instance, although the benefits of olive oil's polyphenols to human health have been validated by many studies, their communication is hindered by lack of discussion between scientific disciplines (Clodoveo et al., 2022), and while the EU Regulation 1924/2006 established a health claim on olive oil polyphenols, no other health claim has been approved (Ibid).

Given the above premises, we are interested in studying Moroccan and Tunisian consumers' preferences for olive oil, and assessing if a health-focused nudge, in the form of a concise, layperson language message unveiling the linkage between polyphenols and healthiness can help overturn consumers' alleged dislike for bitter and pungent, thus promoting consumption of healthier olive oils.¹ While increased awareness can help consumers make more informed food choices, increased understanding of consumers' preferences can help local producers improve their product, and market it more effectively. Therefore, we test the following hypotheses:

H1: Consumers have lower WTP for bitter/pungent olive oils compared to sweet ones before being informed about the health benefits of polyphenols and their relationship with taste.

H2: Information about polyphenol content without further contextualisation has no significant impact on WTP (**H2a**), but introducing information about origin increases consumers' WTP for local oils relative to generic national ones (**H2b**).

H3: Providing information on the relationship between polyphenol content and health benefits increases consumers' WTP for high-polyphenol olive oils relative to sweet ones.

H4: The increase in WTP for high-polyphenol oils relative to low-polyphenol ones persists when consumers are confronted with the bitter/pungent taste.

To validate our hypotheses, we conduct an incentivised laboratory experiment that builds on the Becker–DeGroot–Marschak (BDM) procedure (Becker & DeGroot, 1974) as applied by Lange et al. (2002). We recruit urban consumers in Tunisia and Morocco and test the difference in their WTP across

¹ The discrepancy between consumers' sensory appreciation of olive oil and its actual health benefits makes evaluating the perception of polyphenol content more interesting than focusing on the content of saturated fats, which has no direct relationship with taste.

olive oil profiles and consumers' features, primarily their awareness of polyphenols' benefits and their stated preferences for bitterness/pungency.

The rest of the article is structured as follows. The next section provides an overview of the olive oil sector and of previous studies on consumers' preferences in Morocco and Tunisia. Section 3 illustrates our protocol, data collection procedure, empirical model, and estimation strategy. Then, Section 4 illustrates and discusses the results. Section 5 concludes and derives policy implications.

2. Literature background

Both Tunisia and Morocco are important olive and olive oil producers. In Tunisia in particular, the olive sector holds a prominent position within the country's agricultural and agri-food industries. Approximately 1.8 million hectares, accounting for 79% of the area dedicated to perennial trees and 34% of arable land, are utilised for olive tree cultivation. During the 2019-2020 season, Tunisia stood as the third largest global producer of olive oil (ONAGRI, 2020). More recently, it reached the second position, contributing 5.6% of the world production, surpassed only by Spain (Ben-Hassine et al., 2022a). Approximately 80% of the olive oil production is exported, primary to Spain and Italy, with bulk exports accounting for 85% of Tunisia's olive oil shipments (Ibid).

In Morocco, olives represent the second agricultural production after cereals (MAPMDREF, 2020), accounting for 5% of the agricultural GDP and 7% of agricultural exports (Cour des Comptes du Maroc, 2019). Olive oil covers 19% of the national needs for edible oils (International Olive Council [IOC], 2019), with almost 40% of consumers buying it in large quantity directly from producers in the harvesting period (Interprolive, 2012). This, on the one hand, implies a key role of short supply chains and trust for the supplier on the other hand, the presence of poor-quality olives and olive oil in the market leads to distortions in the perception of quality and thus in the decision-making process regarding purchase (El Badaoui et al., 2017).

In short, olive production is a fundamental component of the agricultural sector in both countries but suffers from economic and environmental challenges, including in maintaining consistent quality standards for internal consumers and to compete on international markets. The predominance of bulk exports causes a loss of identity, resulting in lack of added value (Cour des Comptes du Maroc, 2019). Additionally, bulk commercialisation makes it difficult to develop an effective quality control and traceability system on a national scale, at least in Morocco (Rahmani, 2017). These considerations point to a need of building awareness among consumers to incentivise better market practices in turn.

2.1. Consumers' preferences for olive oil in Tunisia and Morocco

There is a growing body of literature on consumers' preferences for olive oil. This trend is particularly evident for Tunisia while, to the best of our knowledge, there are no peer reviewed studies on Morocco. Most of the extant studies have been published after 2010: before then, the focus has been on olive oil's organoleptic characteristics.

Polyphenol content and taste are among the most widely researched attributes. For instance, Dekhili et al. (2011) found that in both France and Tunisia, taste is the most important out of 13 attributes. This also is the case in Morocco, where taste was indicated as the main driver of purchase decisions by 26.8% of the respondents to a survey, at the top of preferences (Interprolive, 2012). Tunisian consumers generally prefer olive oils with a stronger flavour rather than bland oils (Mtmet et al., 2013). However, there is conflicting evidence surrounding their preferences for pungency and bitterness, with some studies suggesting that they prefer olive oils high in polyphenol (Ben-Hassine et al., 2022b),² and others suggesting that they dislike these (Hassine et al., 2015). Hassine et al. (2014) related Tunisian consumers' taste preferences to the sensory profiles of the olive oils indirectly through other attributes like

² Ben-Hassine et al. (2022b) still say that participants 'appreciated the fruity attribute and, in part, the pungent sensation, whereas they recognise bitterness as a negative attribute,' which somewhat conflicts with their own findings that participants preferred polyphenol rich oils.

cultivar, polyphenol content, and the system used to extract the oil. Opposite to the bulk of the literature, they found that consumers prefer pungent oils. Hassine et al. (2015) suggest that appreciation of bitter and pungent oils is linked to being accustomed to such taste, which could in turn explain why, in the taste preference studies based in the Global North, these attributes are often disliked.

In terms of origin, a literature review by Erraach et al. (2021) found that both country and region are important to consumers, with people from olive oil producing areas generally preferring oils from their own country or region. Chrysochou et al. (2022) found that the country of origin is more important to Tunisian consumers than to consumers from France or the US. Instead, using the same method, Dekhili et al. (2011) found that in Tunisia, opposite to France, the region of origin is more important than the country. One explanation for this is that imported olive oils are common in France but not in Tunisia (Dekhili et al., 2011). Conversely, Mtimet et al. (2013) found that the region of origin does not significantly influence Tunisians' purchasing decisions. Tunisians' attitudes towards regional and quality labels may be influenced by the established habit of purchasing olive oil in bulk from local mills (Dekhili & d'Hauteville, 2009; Mtimet et al., 2013). Furthermore, while origin labels are sometimes used as markers of quality (Erraach et al., 2021), Tunisians are most influenced by the origin of the olive variety, as they value single-variety oils higher (Dekhili & d'Hauteville, 2009). In the only study available for Morocco (Interprolive, 2012), origin was indicated as the main driver of purchase decisions by 11.5% of the respondents, well below taste, and after quality, price, and colour. Interestingly, the same study found that healthiness was the least important attribute, with 8% of the preferences (Ibid).

Besides the above attributes, the type of oil (extra virgin or other) has also been considered in consumers' preferences studies. Chrysochou et al. (2022) found that this is the most influential factor for Tunisian consumers (and those from France and the US). Mtimet et al. (2013) found that Tunisian consumers appreciate the difference between olive pomace oil, virgin olive oil, and extra virgin olive oil (EVOO), and are willing to pay more for the latter two in comparison to the former, and most for extra virgin. In contrast, Dekhili et al. (2011) found that the 'extra virgin' label is not particularly important to Tunisians compared to French consumers. This aligns with what was observed in Morocco, where the lack of a price premium discourages investments in the sector (Rahmani, 2016). However, these preferences may depend on the consumer category, as it may be difficult to distinguish between EVOO and other types when bulk-buying olive oil (Mtimet et al., 2013). Here, we only focus on EVOOs (the best quality product), evaluating them ahead of fieldwork to ensure that they met the required standards to be awarded this label. Indeed, we consider extra virgin, virgin, and pomace oils to be different products. Nevertheless, we check consumers' awareness of the definition of 'extra virgin.'

In the above studies, consumers' preferences were sometimes measured using hedonic ratings of olive oils after taste tests (Ben-Hassine et al., 2022b; Hassine et al., 2014; Hassine et al., 2015) or provision of information about the oils (Dekhili & d'Hauteville, 2009). Best-worst scaling (Chrysochou et al., 2022; Dekhili et al., 2011) and discrete choice experiments (Dekhili & d'Hauteville, 2009) were also used. Instead, we elicit real preferences through incentivisation and register WTP as continuous.

The above overview reveals a need of additional research in Southern Mediterranean olive oil producing countries, primarily Morocco, to investigate if preferences differ significantly from developed countries, where most studies have been conducted to date, and there is a potential for developing a premium internal market.

2.2. Healthiness information in the promotion of olive oil

The provision of information can increase the salience for individual consumers of specific characteristics of a product, particularly those that are not immediately visible, like health and nutrition benefits, or that can be appreciated only in the long-term, like environmental protection, and can thus work as a nudge towards certain consumption choices (Cadario & Chandon, 2020). The impact of information provision on diets has been extensively tested in the literature (Ibid, Arno & Thomas, 2016), usually by means of experiments or randomised controlled trials, and while this approach entails lower costs for public finances compared to monetary incentives, the impact is usually small, if any. For example, in the Pakistan Early Child Development Scale Up Trial by UNICEF, described by White et al. (2014), one group received basic health and nutrition information, while others received additional support.

Children were found to benefit significantly from all the treatments compared to the control, but the outcomes were better in the enhanced groups.

In the case of EVOO, the provision of health information is quite standardised, at least in the Global North, thus limiting the opportunities for conveying the message in alternative ways. The EU health claim usually reported on olive oil bottles states: *‘Olive oil polyphenols contribute to the protection of blood lipids from oxidative stress. Health relationship: protection of LDL particles from oxidative damage.’* However, as argued in Section 1, labels often use excessively technical terminology. In particular, as also reported by Pichierri et al. (2021), the claim regarding polyphenols in EVOO is found to be less understandable than other claims that can be placed on the same product (e.g., health claim vitamin E) and was also less useful in communicating the beneficial characteristics of this product to consumers, making it therefore a less appealing claim. Considering that, our study focus was not to evaluate the impact of the EU health claim on consumers, but rather to focus on the communication and information related to the beneficial aspects of EVOO (i.e. polyphenols content); also considering that this aspect is also linked to an organoleptic component, i.e. the perception of bitterness and pungency, of which polyphenols are the main responsible factors (Vitaglione et al., 2015). Additionally, it is important to emphasise that the study was conducted not in Europe, but in Tunisia and Morocco, where consumers typically purchase olive oil in bulk. As a result, labelling a bottle is not particularly effective; what truly matters is communication within short supply chains, since raising awareness of health benefits and positive sensory characteristics of EVOO is still necessary. Thus, we were interested in assessing the impact of a concise, layperson message linking polyphenol content and taste with healthiness. Therefore, we elaborated the following message, which was refined after pre-testing: *‘A pungent or bitter taste of olive oil indicates higher content of polyphenols. Olive oil polyphenols are good for your health. Therefore, healthier olive oils are likely to be more bitter and pungent.’* The message was translated into Arabic in the final study setup.

3. Data and methods

‘Stated preferences’ may be subject to hypothetical bias (Haghani et al., 2021). Therefore, we reveal consumers’ preferences through an experimental auction (Becker & DeGroot, 1974), where decisions have actual consequences for their welfare through their financial endowment. Such ‘revealed preferences’ were found to have higher external validity (Chang et al., 2010; Levitt & List, 2007; Lusk & Fox, 2003).

3.1. Study protocol

Our auction protocol builds upon the approach by Lange et al. (2002) as adopted by Barlagne et al. (2015) and Bougherara and Combis (2009). It is implemented in a laboratory setting and includes tasting of the product.³ As a proxy of consumers’ preferences, we register their willingness-to-pay (WTP), i.e., a form of valuation related to perception which represents the maximum amount of money they would pay for a product or service described by a given set of attributes. In this article, we focus on consumers’ WTP with respect to olive oil characteristics.

The BDM mechanism is the second most popular elicitation method in the literature after second price auctions (Canavari et al., 2019). Caputo et al. (2023) suggest that real choice experiments (Alfnes & Rickertsen, 2011), which integrate economic incentives by implementing the choices, are preferable as they allow real-time comparison of the options and generate WTP estimates that deviate less from underlying values. We adopt the BDM protocol anyway for three main reasons: first, the collinearity of healthiness, polyphenol levels and pungent/bitter taste prevent us from including these attributes jointly in a choice experiment design; second, tasting can only take place sequentially and thus requires a

³ Our protocol also included the measurement of biometric data to link consumers’ conscious response (their WTP) to their non-conscious responses, namely visual attention and emotions. Visual attention was measured through eye-tracking (Orquin & Loose, 2013), emotions through pupil dilation (Bradley et al., 2008) and facial expression using algorithms that build on the Facial Action Coding System (Ekman & Friesen, 1971). These data are out of the scope of this article and are not discussed further; an analysis of participants’ non-conscious responses along all the stages of the protocol is provided in [omitted for review] (2024).

longitudinal approach; third, we did not have the possibility to gather an auction group in the same place at the same time. Canavari et al. (2019) suggest that this issue could be overcome by relying on two-people groups in different rooms, similar to our data collection context. However, we wanted to avoid the altruistic bidder issue as well as interdependency between participants' decision that could make the process less transparent and undermine trust in the experimental team, which we expect to be already low in a developing country context. Nevertheless, to mitigate the shortcomings of the BDM mechanism and ensure that the WTP values detected are reasonable, during recruitment, we screened potential participants based on their knowledge of the price of one litre of olive oil with good approximation.⁴

In the BDM procedure, participants are asked to evaluate different product profiles along multiple stages, and to state their WTP for each of them at each stage. To avoid the hypothetical bias, at the end of the procedure a product profile, a stage, and a price are extracted, and if the WTP of the consumer for the extracted product in the extracted stage is equal or greater than the extracted price, they must purchase the product at the extracted price using part of their show-up fee; otherwise, they are paid the full fee. In our protocol, we disclose additional information at each stage, with the aim of assessing its impact on WTP.

3.1.1. Attributes and tested olive oil profiles

The number of stages, oil profiles, and the attributes to describe those profiles were selected through an iterative process taking account of our hypotheses, the need of limiting duration to maintain consumers' attention, and the availability of real olive oils characterised by the attributes selected, aiming for a full factorial design. The 'implicit' attributes entailed in our study (Table 1), are five: (a) the taste as detected by consumers through testing; (b) the taste as implicitly described in the label; (c) the origin; (d) the polyphenol content; (e) the healthiness of the oils. However, as pointed out above, there is collinearity between taste, polyphenol content and healthiness: the oils with higher polyphenol content are more bitter/pungent, and healthier. Hence, the attributes are actually two: the origin (local vs national), and the polyphenol content (low vs high), allowing a full factorial design with four profiles. As explained below, we present the latter attribute differently at each stage, revealing the collinearity only at a specific stage. Indeed, according to the extant literature and our hypotheses, these attributes are likely to impact WTP in opposite directions: by releasing additional information at distinct stages, we can assess which element affects consumers' preferences more. Additionally, we define 'local' as coming from the region where the study was being implemented, 'non-local,' from the country in general rather than another specific region which could be related to region-specific perceptions, reducing generalisability.

Table 1. Attributes, levels, and stage of disclosure to consumers.

Attribute	Levels	Stages of disclosure
(a) Taste (sensory)	Sweet/non-pungent; Bitter/pungent	1, 4
(b) Taste (declared)	Sweet/non-pungent; Bitter/pungent	3, 4
(c) Origin	National (Tunisia/Morocco); Local (Sousse/Meknès)	2, 3, 4
(d) Polyphenol content	Low; High	2, 3, 4
(e) Healthiness	Less healthy; Healthier	3, 4

3.1.2. Study setup

Consumers were asked to evaluate the oils along several stages as described in Table 2 below.⁵ At each stage, they received additional information or were given the opportunity to link together pieces of information previously received separately, namely taste, polyphenol content, and healthiness. To ensure independence between the evaluations at each stage, we swapped the order of the oils, creating

⁴ The local experimental team defined an acceptable price range ahead of fieldwork.

⁵ The protocol included a Stage 5 meant to assess the impact of the real bottles and brands on consumers' WTP. However, Stage 5 data are not discussed in this article for two main reasons. First, all the information related to our hypotheses was already disclosed by Stage 4 and the images of the bottles were not large enough for consumers to read the information in the real labels; therefore, Stage 5 cannot be considered to provide *additional* information about the *same* oils. Second, the generic, unbranded bottles shown at Stages 2-4 reproduce more closely the experience of bulk purchasing olive oil; hence, the resulting WTP levels are likely to align better with the real preferences of Tunisian and Moroccan consumers.

four randomisation plans to be used in subsequent days.⁶ We deviated from the standard BDM procedure inasmuch the oil profiles sold in each day was predefined rather than extracted; however, this was not revealed before the auction.⁷ We recorded the WTP in local currency (Tunisian dinars -TND- and Moroccan dinars -MAD-) and for one litre of oil. The selling price was extracted electronically and was never higher than the show-up fee. The entire procedure took place in front of a computer screen.

Table 2. Stages of the protocol: product conditions and information delivered to participants.

Stage	Description of the stage	Example of images seen by consumers	
Stage 1: Tasting	Consumers taste each oil in turn, but see only a mark on the screen.		
Stage 2: Labels	Consumers see generic bottles with information about origin (national vs local) and polyphenol content (low vs high).		
Stage 3: Information about health benefits	First, consumers see a text in Arabic that explains the relationship between bitter taste and health, which is also read aloud by the enumerator. Then, they see similar labels as in stage 2 with information about origin and polyphenol content.		
Stage 4: Tasting and labels	Consumers taste each oil in turn together with the correspondent label information about origin and polyphenol content.		

The differences in the WTP declared by consumers at each stage allow us to test our hypotheses. For instance, if **H1** is true, we would observe lower WTP for bitter/pungent oils at Stage 1. **H2** can be tested by looking at differences between Stages 1 and 2. We introduce the health-related message at Stage 3, thus allowing to test our **H3**. Finally, we explicitly link the actual taste with the rest of the information at Stage 4, allowing to test our **H4**.

In both countries, local researchers defined a preliminary list of ten ‘virgin’ olive oil brands available in the market. These were sensory assessed to select, for each level of the origin attribute (national or local), two profiles with low bitter/pungent and two with high bitter/pungent that could also be considered ‘extra virgin,’ i.e., without any sensory defects. The sensory analysis was performed by trained assessors of the Department of Agricultural and Food Sciences of the University of Bologna, Italy. The procedure abided by the methods defined by EU regulations (Reg. EU 2022/2105 and Reg. EU 2022/2104) and the International Olive Council (IOC/T.20 Doc. No. 15/Rev. 10/2018). In particular, the different samples were sensory profiled according to the intensity of possible defects and the three main ‘positive attributes’ (fruity, bitterness and pungency): the perceived intensity was ranked by each assessor on a continuous scale between 0 and 10 after tasting 15 ml of each oil sample at 28±2°C in the sensory laboratory (IOC/T.20/Doc. No 6/Rev. 1/2007). For each sensory defect and positive attribute,

⁶ As part of the initial instructions, the participants were told that the order of the oils would change between rounds and, therefore, they should not make assumptions based on the order.

⁷ Extracting an oil each day would have required us to purchase four bottles for each consumer, with related issues in terms of budget, and storage space. The participants were told that at the end of the whole process, they would be informed of the brand of olive oil for sale that day.

we computed the median score of the eight tasters to obtain the intensity. Based on this procedure, we selected for the study the EVOOs presented in Table 3. According to EU regulation 2022/2104, the ‘positive attributes’ can be characterised as ‘robust,’ ‘medium,’ or ‘delicate.’ Following the assessment, our oils were categorised as either ‘delicate’ (which we describe as having ‘low’ polyphenol content) or ‘medium’ (‘high’ polyphenol content).

Table 3. Olive oils selected for the study in Tunisia and Morocco, and their characteristics.

Tunisia	Morocco	Origin	Polyphenol content	Profile (symbol)
Safir	El Mallalia	National	Low	Nat. & Low oil (o ₁)
Tesoro del Rio	Ouad Ourika	National	High	Nat. & High oil (o ₂)
Ruspina	Meissara	Local	Low	Loc. & Low oil (o ₃)
Newman’s Own	Volubilia	Local	High	Loc. & High oil (o ₄)

Before embarking in the auction proper, the consumers were explained the mechanism and conducted two training rounds using two completely different products to avoid priming (mobile phones and toothpaste tubes), followed by understanding questions and feedback on their responses. Furthermore, after the stages of the protocol, and before the extraction of the price, they were administered a complementary questionnaire. Among other questions, this included a five-level Likert scale rating the importance of different attributes for their appreciation of olive oil, inspired to the eleven food values by Lusk and Briggeman (2009), reviewed following discussion with local value chain stakeholders. It also included one question to assess the participants’ knowledge of the definition of ‘extra virgin’ as well as one on whether they knew about the relationship between pungent/bitter and healthiness before taking part in the experiment.⁸

The protocol was pre-tested at Copenhagen Business School in May 2022 – and refined according to the feedback obtained – and again with local consumers in the week before the actual fieldwork in each country. The study received ethical approval from relevant bodies in the case study countries. The full protocol as well as the complementary questionnaire are available at the following link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10698832>.

3.2. Data and data analysis

We recruited stratified samples of urban consumers in the cities of Meknès (Morocco) and Sousse (Tunisia). The samples are representative of the cities’ populations in terms of age groups and gender. We filtered potential participants according to four criteria: having no allergy to olive oil; regular consumption of olive oil; being involved in grocery shopping at least from time to time; and, as already mentioned, their knowledge of the price of one litre of olive oil.

The data were recorded partly using the iMotions software version 9.3, which tracked consumers’ facial and eye movements and registered their WTP, partly with Qualtrics, which recorded their responses to the training rounds and the final questionnaire. All texts were in Arabic. The fieldwork took place in September 2022 in Morocco, and in October-November 2022 in Tunisia. Testing on consumer took up to 30 minutes. Two consumers were tested at a time, in different rooms, along several weeks.

The final sample size is 230 in Morocco and 208 in Tunisia, resulting in 4,600 and 4,160 instances of WTP along all the oils and stages, respectively. The WTP for each oil and stage, $WTP_{i,s,o}$, was registered in local currency, but to facilitate cross-country comparison we converted it in \$PPP before analysing the results.⁹

As a first step, we present consumers’ responses in terms of purchasing habits, knowledge of the definition of ‘extra virgin,’ knowledge of the relationship between bitter/pungent and healthiness, and importance of different attributes for the appreciation of olive oil. As a second step, we test the differences in WTP across protocol, polyphenol content, declared taste preferences, declared knowledge of

⁸ While asking this question after the auction could have led to biased responses for social desirability, we could not ask it before as it would have jeopardised the purpose of the study.

⁹ ‘PPP conversion factor, GDP (LCU per international \$),’ available at <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/PA.NUS.PPP> [accessed 22 February 2024].

the relationship between bitter/pungent and healthiness, and combination of these features. Since most variables are binary, we use *t*-tests – one tailed if our hypothesis has direction, two-tailed otherwise. As a last step, we estimate WTP models whose empirical form is described below.

To account for consumers' price expectations, we estimate models for both absolute ($WTP_{i,s,o}$) and relative WTP ($rWTP_{i,s,o}$), obtained dividing $WTP_{i,s,o}$ by the price usually paid by consumer i for one litre of olive oil, declared during recruitment. We also exclude from the analysis three instances of WTP (one in Tunisia, and two in Morocco) that are more than three IQRs above the third quartile of the distribution and could be data entry errors.

For each country, and for both absolute and relative WTP, we test two sets of explanatory variables: (1) the olive oil profiles (brands) and their interaction with the stage; (2) attribute dummies and their interactions with the stage. The coefficients are similar because the design is full factorial, and each profile corresponds to a combination of attribute levels. However, the model with the attribute dummies is more parsimonious because it does not include coefficients for the interaction between attributes, which are instead entailed in the oil profiles. The empirical forms of the two models are the following:

$$WTP_{i,s,o} = \alpha + \beta_{s,o} + \theta c_i + \vartheta t_o + \varphi g_i + \omega a_i + \tau y_i + \varepsilon_i \quad (1)$$

$$WTP_{i,s,o} = \alpha + \gamma_s r_o + \delta_s p_o + \theta c_i + \vartheta t_o + \varphi g_i + \omega a_i + \tau y_i + \varepsilon_i \quad (2)$$

$WTP_{i,s,o}$ is the WTP of consumer i at Stage s , for olive oil o . The β 's in Eq. (1) are oil- and stage-fixed effects. In Eq. (2), r_o is a binary variable for the origin, p_o is a binary variable for polyphenol level, and γ 's and δ 's are stage-fixed coefficients for these two attributes. As controls, we include a dummy for the computer (out of two) used by i , and thus for the 'room context,' c_i ; the order in which the oil was shown according to the randomisation plan, t_o ; i 's gender g_i , age a_i , and income level y_i . In Eq. (1), olive oil o_1 at Stage s_1 is the baseline, thus $\beta_{1,1}$ is omitted. In Eq. (2), the baseline levels are national origin r_o , and low polyphenol content p_o . The Greek letters indicate the coefficients to be estimated, and where the same letter is used, the coefficients correspond between the two specifications. In both Equations, ε_i is an unobserved, individual-specific error term.

We estimate separate models for Tunisia and Morocco. Since the WTP is censored at zero, we use Tobit models with individual-specific random effects (Goldberger, 1964), estimated using maximum likelihood. To account for correlation between the observations relative to the same consumer across stages and oils, we cluster the standard errors at individual level. Moreover, the inclusion of socio-demographics and other control variables, such as the computer used, reduces observed individual heterogeneity. To assess the performance of the models, we report the Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC; Schwarz, 1978), and the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC; Findley & Parzen, 1998), which penalise the models with more parameters. No one in Morocco declared zero WTP (and only one in Tunisia); therefore, the estimated coefficients are the same as an OLS model.

4. Results and discussions

In this section, we discuss the results of our study. First, we present descriptive statistics from the complementary survey, including stated preferences for olive oil. Then, we analyse WTP values with respect to the various attributes and stages of the protocol, to test if our hypotheses are supported.

4.1. Descriptive statistics, oil consumption and stated preferences

In Tunisia, 52.9% of the respondents were female, and the age ranged between 20 and 75 years (median 41.5). In Morocco, 48.3% were female and the age ranged between 18 and 77 (median 47). While the distribution by age and gender is in line with the city populations due to stratification, the samples differ in terms of income and level of education, probably because of the more significant presence of high education institutions in Sousse. Hence, the Tunisian sample can be considered closer to the samples of students generally involved in laboratory experiments conducted in the Global North.

Virtually all the participants consumed olive oil every day, or at least few times per week. The form of purchase was similar, with a large prevalence of bulk purchases and limited reliance on bottled oils,

in line with the literature (Dekhili & d’Hauteville, 2009; Mtimet et al., 2013; Interprolive, 2012). At Stages 2-4, we used as stimuli generic, unbranded bottles, like those which can be filled up when bulk purchasing olive oil.¹⁰ Furthermore, the most common pattern was to purchase olive oil once a year (during the production season), but with a large difference between countries, as Moroccans were much more likely to do so (80% vs 49%).

Table 1. Descriptive statistics for key sample characteristics and explanatory variables, by country.

Variable	Value	Morocco		Tunisia		p-value ¹
		n	%	n	%	
Computer	2 nd computer	111	48.3	101	48.6	0.951
Gender	Female	111	48.3	110	52.9	0.335
Age	Years ²	45.56	14.51	42.02	12.89	0.008
Monthly income ³	Low	58	25.2	1	0.5	0.000
	Mid-to-low	84	36.5	44	21.2	
	Middle	43	18.7	81	38.9	
	Mid-to-high	22	9.6	60	28.9	
	High	23	10.0	22	10.6	
Level of education	Literate with no qualifications	43	18.7	8	3.9	0.001
	Primary	50	21.7	22	10.6	
	Secondary	82	35.7	48	23.1	
	University	45	19.6	92	44.2	
	Post-university	10	4.4	38	18.3	
Frequency of olive oil consumption	Once a month	1	0.4	1	0.5	0.080
	More than once a month	0	0.0	5	2.4	
	Once a week	13	5.7	6	2.9	
	More than once a week	54	23.5	33	15.9	
	Every day	162	70.4	163	78.4	
Frequency of olive oil purchase	Few times per week	9	3.9	79	38.0	0.000
	Once a week	2	0.9	6	2.9	
	Few times per month	6	2.6	5	2.4	
	Once a month	17	7.4	11	5.3	
	Less than once a month	9	3.9	5	2.4	
	Once a year	185	80.4	102	49.0	
	More rarely	2	0.9	0	0.0	
Never	0	0.0	0	0.0		
Way of acquiring olive oil	In a bottle	14	6.1	10	4.8	0.355
	Both	29	12.6	22	10.6	
	In bulk	187	81.3	176	84.6	
Producing one’s own oil	Yes	89	38.7	137	65.9	0.000
Family or friends providing oil	Yes	167	72.6	156	75.0	0.571
Either of the two above	Yes	189	82.2	188	90.4	0.013
Knowing the definition of extra-virgin	Yes	124	53.9	92	44.2	0.043
Choosing the right definition	Yes	95	41.3	30	14.4	0.000
Taste preferences	I am indifferent to it	3	1.3	3	1.4	0.098
	Not pungent/bitter at all	39	17.0	23	11.1	
	Slightly pungent/bitter	113	49.1	99	47.6	
	Pungent/bitter	49	21.3	62	29.8	
	Very pungent/bitter	26	11.3	21	10.1	
Taste preferences binary	Like pungent/bitter or very p/b	75	33.0	83	40.5	0.109
Knowledge of the taste/health relationship	Yes	191	83.0	165	79.3	0.321
Price paid usually	\$PPP ²	13.07	3.68	14.30	3.60	0.001

Notes: The total number of observations is 230 in Morocco and 208 in Tunisia for all the variables apart from ‘Taste preferences binary,’ whose value is missing for those who responded, ‘I am indifferent to it.’ ¹ Difference between countries: two-tailed *t*-tests for binary and continuous variable, Kruskal-Wallis tests (χ^2 with ties) for categorical variables. ² Mean and standard deviation. ³ The questionnaire reported actual income threshold relevant for the country where the experiment was being conducted.

Almost two thirds of the Tunisians and two fifths of the Moroccans in our sample, declared that they produce their own oil; and around three quarters in both countries, that they receive oil from friends and

¹⁰ The price usually paid by the consumers for one litre of olive oils, detected at the recruitment stage, does not differ significantly depending on the way of purchasing ($\chi^2(2) = 0.698$, $p = 0.149$ for Tunisia, and $\chi^2(2) = 3.81$, $p = 0.149$ for Morocco based on a Kruskal-Wallis test), suggesting that this aspect is unlikely to bias the results.

relatives. Hence, 90% of the Tunisians and 82% of the Moroccans could rely on at least one of these supply sources. This is, again, in line with the literature, that local olive oils are widely consumed (Rahmani, 2016).

We only focus on ‘extra virgin’ oils, and the products were tested to ensure that they met the required standards to be marketed as such. Hence, we asked our participants if they knew the difference between ‘virgin’ and ‘extra virgin.’ While around half of the participants in either country declared that they did, when asked to select the right response between four options, the gap between countries was significant ($t(436) = 6.50, p < 0.001$), with Moroccans much more likely to respond correctly.

There was a slight prevalence of participants preferring relatively sweet oils. However, the distribution of taste preferences differed only marginally between countries ($\chi^2(1) = 2.74, p = 0.098$), and not at all when turned into a binary variable. Furthermore, around four fifths of the respondents in both countries declared that they were already aware of the relationship between taste and healthiness. In Tunisia, the correlation between taste preferences and knowledge of this relationship was non-significant ($\chi^2(4) = 5.88, p = 0.208$), while in Morocco, those who declared to know this relationship beforehand, tended to prefer relatively more bitter/pungent oils ($\chi^2(4) = 67.10, p < 0.001$).

Before discussing consumers’ revealed preferences, we show their responses to the Likert scale rating the importance of different attributes for their appreciation of olive oil (Table 4). The ranking of the attributes in term of average importance score is similar between countries, with limited exceptions, but the values differ significantly, being generally higher for Morocco. ‘Taste’ is deemed the most important attribute in both countries, in line with the literature from both Tunisia (Dekhili et al., 2011) and Morocco (Interprolive, 2012). ‘Price and ‘trust for the producer,’ which was added to the scale following discussion with local stakeholders, to reflect the short nature of the local olive oil supply chains and the role of networks, also rank high in both countries. Noteworthy, ‘proximity to the production area’ and ‘origin’ rank rather low, confirming what already found in past studies for Tunisia (Mtimet et al., 2013) and Morocco (Interprolive, 2012), and providing initial evidence against our **H2b**.

Table 4. Importance of different elements for consumers’ appreciation of olive oil.

Country	Tunisia	Morocco	<i>p</i> -value
Taste	4.67	4.80	0.011
Trust	4.48	4.42	0.419
Colour	4.24	4.38	0.066
Price	4.22	4.41	0.018
Own milling	4.00	4.32	0.002
Olives	3.95	4.28	0.002
Seller	3.93	3.49	0.000
Labels	3.84	3.18	0.000
Packaging	3.83	4.49	0.000
Fluidity	3.75	4.30	0.000
Origin	3.68	3.97	0.005
Proximity	3.36	3.57	0.045
What others do	3.05	3.37	0.004
Advertisement	2.81	2.30	0.000

Notes: Importance assessed on a scale from 1 = ‘not important at all’ to 5 = ‘very important.’ The *p*-values refer to a two-tailed *t*-test.

4.2. Experimental results and the impact of the nudge

The average WTP across all olive oil profiles in Stages 1-4 was 14.24\$PPP in Tunisia and 25.54\$PPP in Morocco ($p < 0.000$). For Tunisia, it does not differ significantly from the average price paid for one litre of olive oil, registered during recruitment (14.30\$PPP, $p = 0.566$), but for Morocco, it differs hugely (13.07\$PPP, $p < 0.000$). Thus, the relative WTP is almost double in Morocco compared to Tunisia (2.02 vs 1.03, $p < 0.000$). The Moroccan figures seem to support what observed by Caputo et al. (2023), that the BDM mechanism produces higher WTP estimates, and may be driven by the lower level of education of Moroccan participants, which may have led many of them to see bottled olive oil as a ‘positional good’. Additionally, the WTP values for Morocco are in line with the average price of bottled oil in that

country, which in 2026 ranged between 50-120 MAD (13-31\$PPP), with no significant differences between typologies (Rahmani, 2016).

Tables 5 and 6 report the results of *t*-tests of differences in WTP for specific oil profiles and consumers' categories between rounds. The results of more *t*-tests are provided in Tables 9 and 10 in Appendix. Table 7 reports the estimates of the Tobit models with the attributes as explanatory variables, while Table 8 in Appendix contains the estimates of the model with the olive oil profiles. Based on the BIC and AIC, the models for Tunisia display a better goodness-of-fit than those for Morocco, and those for relative WTP display a better goodness-of-fit than those for absolute WTP, although we find no significant differences in the direction and relative sizes of the coefficients.

Based on stated preferences above, we could argue that in both countries there is a slight preference for oils that are 'not bitter/pungent at all' or 'slightly bitter/pungent.' Experimental results do not confirm this but do not suggest that consumers prefer bitter/pungent oils either. Indeed, in neither of the countries the WTP at Stage 1 differs significantly based on taste. This is valid for both Tunisia, where consumers were willing to pay 13.52\$PPP for bitter/pungent and 12.92\$PPP for sweet oils (p 0.123), and for Morocco, where the WTP was respectively 24.82\$PPP and 24.02\$PPP (p 0.444) (Tables 9 and 10). However, in the models in Tables 7, where controls are included, the coefficients for high polyphenol content are significant and positive in Tunisia, suggesting a slight preference for bitter/pungent oils in that country *ceteris paribus*. This might be driven by a bitterer / more pungent taste of Tunisian oils, to which consumers may have got used, and is not true for Morocco. Noteworthy, the difference in WTP across polyphenol levels remains non-significant when considering separately the consumers aware or unaware of the link between bitter/pungent and healthiness, or those who declared in the survey to like or dislike bitter/pungent olive oils (Tables 9 and 10). The only exception is represented by consumers who declared to prefer bitter/pungent oils in Tunisia, whose WTP for these oils was significantly higher (p 0.024). Therefore, **H1 is not verified**: consumers do not particularly dislike bitter/pungent oils before being informed about the health benefits of polyphenols and their relationship with taste, and in Tunisia there is even some evidence in the opposite direction. Therefore, our results provide some slight support for Ben-Hassine et al. (2022b) over Hassine et al. (2015) but cannot provide a clear response in terms of taste preferences of Moroccan consumers.

Table 5. WTP and difference between rounds for olive oils with low and high polyphenol content, and for consumers unaware and aware of the link with healthiness, in Tunisia.

Group	Sample size ¹	Stage 1	Stage 2	Stage 3	Stage 4
All olive oil profiles	829-831	13.22	14.38 1.167***	14.71 0.327***	14.66 -0.040
Low polyphenol oils	415-416	12.92	13.88 0.955***	13.08 -0.803***	13.39 0.324**
High polyphenol oils	413-416	13.52	14.89 1.378***	16.35 1.462***	15.93 -0.404***
Low polyphenol oils, unaware consumers ²	86	13.73	15.11 1.377***	14.27 -0.836**	14.53 0.258
High polyphenol oils, unaware consumers ²	86	14.45	15.12 0.676*	17.25 2.127***	16.45 -0.799**
Low polyphenol oils, aware consumers ²	329-330	12.71	13.56 0.845	12.76 -0.794***	13.10 0.341**
High polyphenol oils, aware consumers ²	327-330	13.27	14.83 1.562***	16.11 1.287***	15.80 -0.301*

Notes: For each group, the first line reports the average WTP in that round for the oils and consumers specified, the second line reports the average difference between that round and the previous one, and the significance level (*** 0.01, ** 0.05, * 0.10) in one-tailed or two-tailed *t*-tests ($\Pr(T < 0)$, $\Pr(|T| > 0)$, $\Pr(T > 0)$). ¹ It indicates the number of observations per round, which can vary between rounds. ² Consumers are classified as 'Aware' or 'Unaware' based on their previous knowledge of the relationship between bitter/pungent and healthiness.

Table 6. WTP and difference between rounds for olive oils with low and high polyphenol content, and for consumers unaware and aware of the link with healthiness, in Morocco.

Group	Sample size	Stage 1	Stage 2	Stage 3	Stage 4
All olive oil profiles	908-920	24.42	24.57	26.42	26.74

			0.237	1.904***	0.179
Low polyphenol oils	454-460	24.02	23.69 -0.181	23.32 -0.424*	24.30 0.925***
High polyphenol oils	454-460	24.82	25.43 0.652	29.52 4.293***	29.18 -0.567
Low polyphenol oils, unaware consumers	78	18.70	21.64 2.943**	21.79 0.149	21.73 -0.056
High polyphenol oils, unaware consumers	78	17.67	21.85 4.179***	28.04 6.182***	26.34 -1.694*
Low polyphenol oils, aware consumers	376-382	25.11	24.12 -0.825*	23.63 -0.543*	24.83 1.129***
High polyphenol oils, aware consumers	376-382	26.28	26.17 -0.070	29.83 3.902***	29.76 -0.334

Notes: See Notes to Table 5.

To test **H2**, we look at the difference in WTP between Stage 1 and Stage 2, when the labels about polyphenol content and origin were introduced. In Tunisia, we observe a significant increase in WTP for all the olive oils regardless of their attributes (+1.17\$PPP, $p < 0.001$), which remains significant for different subsets of consumers and for oils with different polyphenol content, with the unsurprising exception of low-polyphenol oils when it comes to aware consumers (Table 5). Instead, Moroccan consumers show no significant variation on average (+0.237\$PPP, $p = 0.563$) but a significant increase in the WTP for all the oils among unaware consumers and, again unsurprisingly, a marginally significant decrease in the WTP for low-polyphenol oils among aware consumers (Table 6). The coefficients for local origin at Stage 2 in Table 7 are significant and positive for Tunisia, although the size is one third the size of the coefficients for polyphenol and becomes non-significant already at Stage 3. In turn, local origin seems not to have a significant impact on WTP in Morocco. These results are confirmed by the t -test in Tables 9 and 10, where the WTP does not differ significantly depending on origin in any stage and in neither Tunisia, nor Morocco.¹¹ Hence, **H2b** is **not verified**: *introducing information about origin does not increase consumers' WTP for local olive oils relative to generic national ones*. Our findings confirm what argued by Mtimet et al. (2013) for Tunisia as well as the low importance of origin for Moroccan consumers (Interprolive, 2012) and are in line with the stated preferences described above.

The WTP figures in Table 5 suggest that the label about polyphenol content introduced at Stage 2 does have a significant impact, although not trivial. While in the overall Tunisian sample the WTP increases regardless of the polyphenol content, if consumers are divided based on their previous knowledge of the relationship between bitter/pungent and healthiness, we see that the WTP for high-polyphenol olive oils increases more among aware consumers (+1.56\$PPP vs +0.68\$PPP) and the WTP for low-polyphenol oils increases significantly only among unaware consumers. In Morocco only unaware consumers experience a significant increase in WTP, larger for high-polyphenol oils (+4.18\$PPP vs 2.94\$PPP); aware consumers see marginally significant decrease in their WTP for low-polyphenol oils (-0.83\$PPP). The coefficients in Table 7 further suggest that *ceteris paribus*, at Stage 2 the WTP for high-polyphenol oils becomes significantly higher than for low-polyphenol oils in both countries.¹² These results suggest that **H2a** is **not verified**: *a label about polyphenol content impacts WTP, positively in most instances, even without further contextualisation*. The reason is unclear for consumers unaware of the link with healthiness, while for aware consumers, the label may have increased the saliency of what already suggested via the taste. The impact of polyphenol labels has not been tested previously in these countries.

To test **H3**, we focus on the difference in WTP between Stages 2 and Stage 3. The estimates in Table 7 show that at Stage 3, *ceteris paribus*, the WTP for high-polyphenol (healthy) oils is significantly higher than the WTP for low-polyphenol oils. This is confirmed by the estimates in Table 8, where the profiles are used instead: the coefficients for high-polyphenol oils (o_2 and o_4) are significant and

¹¹ Additional t -tests show that the variation in WTP between Stages 1 and 2 is significantly larger for local than for national oils in Tunisia (+1.46\$PPP vs +0.88\$PPP, $t(828) = 1.74$, $p = 0.041$ in a one-tailed test); however, the resulting WTP does not differ significantly in either stage. In turn, the variation does not differ significantly depending on origin in Morocco (-0.03\$PPP vs +0.50\$PPP, $t(913) = -0.64$, $p = 0.740$ in a one-tailed test).

¹² Additional t -tests show that the variation in WTP between Stages 1 and 2 does not differ significantly depending on the polyphenol content, neither in Tunisia (+1.38\$PPP for high vs +0.96\$PPP for low, $t(828) = 1.27$, $p = 0.206$) nor in Morocco (0.65\$PPP vs -0.18\$PPP, $t(913) = 1.016$, $p = 0.310$).

positive in both countries, while those for low-polyphenol oils (o_1 and o_3) do not differ significantly from the baseline.

If we split consumers based on their prior awareness of the linkage between polyphenol content, taste and health benefits (Tables 5 and 6), we observe, as expected, that the increase in WTP for high-polyphenol oils is larger among previously unaware consumers (+2.13\$PPP vs +1.29\$PPP in Tunisia, and +6.18\$PPP vs +3.90\$PPP in Morocco). In turn, the WTP for low-polyphenol oils decreases significantly regardless of awareness in Tunisia, and among aware consumers in Morocco. The ‘advantage’ of high-polyphenol oils (already significant in the overall sample) increases from around 1\$PPP to more than 3\$PPP in Tunisia, and from less than 2\$PPP to more than 6\$PPP in Morocco and becomes significant (which was not the case previously) among unaware consumers (Tables 9 and 10). Even the Moroccan consumers who stated not to like bitter/pungent oils declare significantly higher WTP for high-polyphenol oils (Table 10). Hence, our **H3** is **strongly supported**: *providing information about healthiness increases consumers’ WTP for pungent (healthier) oils relative to non-pungent ones*, particularly among previously unaware consumers. This is particularly noteworthy in Morocco, where ‘health’ ranked as the least important choice criterion in previous studies (Interpolive, 2012).

Table 7. Tobit models for absolute and relative WTP in Tunisia and Morocco, with attributes as explanatory variables.

Variables	Tunisia		Morocco	
	WTP	Relative WTP	WTP	Relative WTP
Stage 1 # Local	-0.525***	-0.035***	0.708	0.061*
Stage 2 # Local	0.471***	0.035***	0.248	0.018
Stage 3 # Local	0.137	0.012	0.349	0.021
Stage 4 # Local	0.101	0.010	0.277	0.024
Stage 1 # High	0.469***	0.032**	0.871	0.062
Stage 2 # High	1.397***	0.105***	1.709***	0.139***
Stage 3 # High	3.023***	0.223***	5.700***	0.438***
Stage 4 # High	2.625***	0.192***	5.446***	0.429***
Computer 2 (baseline: Computer 1)	-0.040	0.013	3.464**	0.320**
Order of the oil 2nd (baseline: 1st)	-0.203	-0.011	0.914	0.065
Order of the oil 3rd (baseline: 1st)	0.086	0.010	0.540	0.046
Order of the oil 4th (baseline: 1st)	0.292	0.022	1.170***	0.097***
Gender female (Baseline: Male)	0.449	0.041	9.201***	0.560***
Age in years	0.010	-0.001	0.064	0.004
Mid-low income (baseline: Low)	-1.450	0.355***	4.417**	0.274
Middle income (baseline: Low)	-1.838***	0.337***	4.418*	0.298
Mid-high income (baseline: Low)	-2.967***	0.267***	1.940	0.041
High income (baseline: Low)	-3.475***	0.293***	1.467	0.075
Constant term	14.837***	0.640***	11.148***	1.054***
N	3,322	3,322	3,663	3,663
Pseudo R ²	0.012	0.054	0.013	0.023
Log likelihood	-10,228.61	-1,784.75	-15,427.94	-6,231.48
AIC	20,495.22	3,607.50	30,895.88	12,502.97
BIC	20,611.28	3,723.56	31,020.01	12,627.09

Finally, we test **H4** by focusing on the difference in WTP between Stage 3 and Stage 4, when consumers tasted the oils again. The estimates Table 7 show that the WTP for high-polyphenol oils is significantly higher compared to the baseline but smaller compared to Stage 3 in both countries. Such dynamics are confirmed by the coefficients for Stage 4 and high-polyphenol oils in Table 8, which are significantly positive but, except for o_2 in Morocco, smaller than at Stage 3. Additional t -tests show that the WTP for high-polyphenol oils decreases slightly in Tunisia (-0.40\$PPP), and does not change in Morocco, while the WTP for low-polyphenol oils increases significantly compared to Stage 3 in both countries (Tables 5 and 6). Noteworthy, the drop in WTP for high-polyphenol oils is larger among (previously) unaware consumers, and marginally significant in Morocco. Consequently, the difference in favour of healthier oils shrinks from more than 3\$PPP to around 2.50\$PPP in Tunisia and from more than 6\$PPP to slightly less than 5\$PPP in Morocco, but remains significant in all subgroups regardless

of awareness and stated preferences.¹³ Hence, **H4 is supported**: *the relative increase in WTP for high-polyphenol oils persists even when consumers face the bitter/pungent taste but the gap becomes smaller*. We can thus argue that the impact of information is persisting.

Beside our hypotheses, the models in Table 8 and 7 reveal interesting, often country-specific, patterns concerning the control variables. First, in neither country the age of the consumers is significantly related to their WTP, while in Morocco, female consumers are willing to pay more than male consumers *ceteris paribus* (+9.20\$PPP on average). In Tunisia, the better off the household, the *lower* the WTP of the consumer, while in Morocco, only mid-low-income consumers show significantly higher WTP than low-income consumers. This result suggests that bottled oils may be perceived as a 'positional good' by poor consumers, who are thus willing to pay more for it. Instead, if considering the relative WTP, all the groups in Tunisia seem to be willing to pay more than low-income consumers, with limited differences between groups. Finally, the coefficients for the order in which the oils were presented to consumers reveal an increase in WTP for the fourth and last oil in a stage, more pronounced in Morocco. This result confirms the importance of controlling for the order in experiments, as found by Krucien et al. (2017) in a study on discrete choice experiments. In Morocco, we also detect a significant computer (room) effect.

5. Conclusions and policy implications

We presented the results of a laboratory experiment aimed at detecting the preferences for national brands of olive oils in Morocco and Tunisia. We focused exclusively on olive oils produced in the two countries considered. Indeed, despite the difference that national or imported origin could make to consumers' preferences, the objective of the project 'FoodLAND – Food and Local, Agricultural and Nutritional Diversity,' within which this study was run, is to favour the development of local, healthy food products. Equally, with a view to promoting quality, we only considered 'extra virgin' olive oils. Therefore, we devoted particular care to identifying olive oil profiles presenting the selected characteristics, and which could be defined as 'extra virgin,' i.e., did not present any sensory defects.

We tested whether the provision of information about the health benefits of bitter/pungent oils resulted in higher WTP for these products even if such sensory features tend to be disliked. Participant consumers from the two countries did not show significantly lower WTP and thus preference for bitter/pungent oils before receiving the health-related nudge. We also found that local origin did not result in higher WTP compared to generic national origin, while high polyphenol content often did, regardless of the participants' awareness of related health benefits. A concise message about health benefits increased WTP for bitter/pungent oils relative to sweet ones, and the impact persisted, net of a small rebound effect, after the respondents experienced again the sensory attribute. These patterns were similar in Tunisia and Morocco.

Our results allow us to draw recommendations for promoting the consumption of healthier olive oil among urban consumers in our case study countries, which could help revert the move away from traditional Mediterranean diets (El Rhazi et al., 2012), and potentially reduce dependence on imports (Drogue et al., 2019). First, our participants showed limited awareness of what constitutes a 'high quality' oil in theoretical terms (i.e., definition of 'extra virgin'), particularly in Tunisia, but they could appreciate quality when tasting, as shown by WTP values for bitter/pungent oils that are not significantly lower. This is a solid basis to build upon for advertising quality olive oils. Second, 'local origin' does not seem to be a value added, at least for olive oil and in the regions considered. Even if we did not compare national and imported oils, our participants appreciated 'national' in the same measure as 'local.' This might be a challenge when promoting more localised value chains, but also suggests that consumers may equally appreciate olive oils from other regions in their country.

Third, a concise message about health benefits was effective in driving preferences, and the impact persisted despite (sensory) information which could push in the opposite direction. We did not use the official EU health claim (which may have limited or no meaning to a layperson) and argue that more

¹³ The difference among previously unaware consumers in Morocco is still large (over 4.50\$PPP) but only significant in a one-tailed *t*-test ($t(154) = 1.42, p = 0.079$).

efforts are made to communicate health as well as other food-related information in a way that is meaningful to the average consumer. Instead of actual branded bottles, we used standard glass bottles with Arabic text on it, suggesting that the message could be reported on the containers used for bulk purchases, effectively reaching Moroccan and Tunisia consumers despite their practice of bulk-purchasing olive oil. Such recommendations apply to both countries but in Tunisia, consumer WTP is lower on average, and the impact of health information less persistent, calling for strategies which are tailored to country-specific conditions.

Our research presents some limitations. First, even if we filtered participants based on their prior knowledge of the price of one litre of olive oil, most of them are used to purchasing oil in bulk, thus they might not purchase bottled olive oil. Nevertheless, incentivisation allowed to reduce the hypothetical bias. Second, due to the necessity of identifying actual olive oils and avoiding overwhelming consumers, we had to limit the number of attributes and their levels, meaning that we excluded additional attributes that may influence real-life choices. Third, also to avoid overwhelming participants, we introduced more than one piece of information at the same stage (namely, origin and polyphenol content), which complicates the identification of attribute-specific effects. Despite such limitations, to the best of our knowledge this is the first study to test consumers' preferences for olive oil, and the impact of health information, in Tunisia and Morocco using a non-hypothetical approach, and the first to do so by applying the same protocol in both countries. Among other amendments, future research could add more stages or include a third tasting while consumers observe the real, branded bottles.

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Author contribution statement

SP: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Methodology, Software Supervision, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing; **CB:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Methodology, Supervision, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing; **JC:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Funding acquisition, Methodology, Project administration, Resources, Software, Supervision, Writing – review & editing; **NM:** Funding acquisition, Investigation, Resources, Supervision, Writing – original draft; **CT:** Funding acquisition, Investigation, Resources, Supervision, Writing – original draft; **MT:** Funding acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Resources, Writing – review & editing; **IW:** Visualization, Writing – original draft.

Ethics statement

Ethical approval for this study was obtained from the Council of the National Authority for the Protection of Personal Data for Tunisia (No. 20-01-1096 of 12/2020), and from the Commission of Research, Continuing Education, and Partnership of the National School of Agriculture of Meknès for

Morocco (No. 1452/D/ENA of 02/11/2020). Written informed consent was obtained from the participants ahead of starting the experiment.

Data availability statement

The data used in this study are freely available at the following link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10698832>. The Stata do file used for to implement the analysis will be made available by the authors upon reasonable request.

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Appendix

Table 8. Tobit models for absolute and relative WTP in Tunisia and Morocco, with olive oil profiles as explanatory variables.

Variables	Tunisia		Morocco	
	WTP	Relative WTP	WTP	Relative WTP
Stage 1 # o ₂ (baseline: Stage 1 # o ₁)	-0.382	-0.022	1.049	0.082
Stage 1 # o ₃ (baseline: Stage 1 # o ₁)	-1.375***	-0.089***	0.887	0.082*
Stage 1 # o ₄ (baseline: Stage 1 # o ₁)	0.091	0.013	1.495**	0.125**
Stage 2 # o ₁ (baseline: Stage 1 # o ₁)	0.218	0.024	-0.390	-0.028
Stage 2 # o ₂ (baseline: Stage 1 # o ₁)	1.149**	0.094***	2.016**	0.172***
Stage 2 # o ₃ (baseline: Stage 1 # o ₁)	0.224	0.024	0.555	0.052
Stage 2 # o ₄ (baseline: Stage 1 # o ₁)	1.413***	0.113***	1.747**	0.146**
Stage 3 # o ₁ (baseline: Stage 1 # o ₁)	-0.778*	-0.049	-0.175	-0.007
Stage 3 # o ₂ (baseline: Stage 1 # o ₁)	2.499***	0.192***	4.967***	0.391***
Stage 3 # o ₃ (baseline: Stage 1 # o ₁)	-0.386	-0.019	-0.390	-0.026
Stage 3 # o ₄ (baseline: Stage 1 # o ₁)	2.982***	0.230***	6.884***	0.528***
Stage 4 # o ₁ (baseline: Stage 1 # o ₁)	-0.081	0.002	0.738	0.075
Stage 4 # o ₂ (baseline: Stage 1 # o ₁)	2.080***	0.163***	5.885***	0.470***
Stage 4 # o ₃ (baseline: Stage 1 # o ₁)	-0.445	-0.019	0.716	0.065
Stage 4 # o ₄ (baseline: Stage 1 # o ₁)	2.567***	0.194***	5.377***	0.436***
Computer 2 (baseline: Computer 1)	-0.039	0.013	3.463**	0.319**
Order of the oil 2 nd (baseline: 1 st)	-0.165	-0.009	0.913	0.065
Order of the oil 3 rd (baseline: 1 st)	0.166	0.015	0.544	0.046
Order of the oil 4 th (baseline: 1 st)	0.327*	0.024*	1.164***	0.097***
Gender female (Baseline: Male)	0.449	0.041	9.203***	0.560***
Age in years	0.010	-0.001	0.064	0.004
Mid-low income (baseline: Low)	-1.451	0.355***	4.416**	0.274
Middle income (baseline: Low)	-1.839***	0.337***	4.418*	0.298
Mid-high income (baseline: Low)	-2.967***	0.267***	1.941	0.041
High income (baseline: Low)	-3.475***	0.293***	1.468	0.076
Constant term	15.150***	0.656***	11.099***	1.043***
N	3,322	3,322	3,663	3,663
Pseudo R ²	0.013	0.056	0.013	0.023
Log likelihood	-10,222.34	-1,779.81	-15,426.54	-6,230.16
AIC	20,496.68	3,611.611	30,907.08	12,514.32
BIC	20,655.49	3,770.428	31,074.64	12,681.89

Notes: For the symbols indicating the olive oil profiles, see Table 3.

Table 9. WTP across all rounds and in specific rounds for different sub-samples and groups, in Tunisia.

Sample	Groups	Obs. ⁴	All stages	Stage 1	Stage 2	Stage 3	Stage 4
All consumers	Low polyphenol oils	1,662	13.32	12.92	13.88	13.08	13.39
	High polyphenol oils	1,660	15.17	13.52	14.89	16.35	15.93
	Pr($T > t $)		0.000	0.123	0.004	0.000	0.000
All consumers	Higher WTP for sweet oils ¹	707	14.47	13.59	15.64	15.50	13.45
	Higher WTP for pungent oils ¹	2,615	14.18	13.03	13.85	14.64	14.84
	Pr($T > t $)		0.213	0.162	0.000	0.232	0.014
All consumers	National origin (Tunisia)	1,661	14.22	13.44	14.32	14.49	14.63
	Local origin (Sousse)	1,661	14.27	12.99	14.45	14.92	14.69
	Pr($T > t $)		0.814	0.242	0.705	0.266	0.868
Consumers not liking pungent ²	Low polyphenol oils	974	13.35	13.21	13.78	13.05	13.36
	High polyphenol oils	975	14.97	13.48	14.83	16.05	15.54
	Pr($T > t $)		0.000	0.637	0.021	0.000	0.000
Consumers liking pungent ²	Low polyphenol oils	664	13.27	12.43	14.04	13.15	13.46
	High polyphenol oils	661	15.42	13.53	14.92	16.77	16.47
	Pr($T > t $)		0.000	0.024	0.126	0.000	0.000
High polyphenol oils	Consumers not liking pungent ²	975	14.97	13.48	14.83	16.05	15.54
	Consumers liking pungent ²	661	15.42	13.53	14.92	16.77	16.47
	Pr($T > t $)		0.103	0.908	0.858	0.217	0.110
Low polyphenol oils	Consumers not liking pungent ²	974	13.35	13.21	13.78	13.05	13.36
	Consumers liking pungent ²	664	13.27	12.43	14.04	13.15	13.46
	Pr($T > t $)		0.769	0.206	0.630	0.841	0.829
Unaware consumers ³	Low polyphenol oils	344	14.41	13.73	15.11	14.27	14.53
	High polyphenol oils	344	15.82	14.45	15.12	17.25	16.45
	Pr($T > t $)		0.004	0.459	0.990	0.003	0.049
Aware consumers ³	Low polyphenol oils	1,318	13.03	12.71	13.56	12.76	13.10
	High polyphenol oils	1,316	15.00	13.27	14.83	16.11	15.80
	Pr($T > t $)		0.000	0.176	0.001	0.000	0.000
High polyphenol oils	Unaware consumers ³	344	15.82	14.45	15.12	17.25	16.45
	Aware consumers ³	1,316	15.00	13.27	14.83	16.11	15.80
	Pr($T > t $)		0.014	0.048	0.620	0.106	0.347
Low polyphenol oils	Unaware consumers ³	344	14.41	13.73	15.11	14.27	14.53
	Aware consumers ³	1,318	13.03	12.71	13.56	12.76	13.10
	Pr($T > t $)		0.000	0.168	0.013	0.012	0.015
Higher WTP for pungent oils ¹	Low polyphenol oils	1,308	12.70	11.96	12.68	12.73	13.24
	High polyphenol oils	1,307	15.66	14.09	15.02	16.55	16.44
	Pr($T > t $)		0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Higher WTP for sweet oils ¹	Low polyphenol oils	354	15.60	14.78	16.69	16.92	14.41
	High polyphenol oils	353	13.34	12.40	14.59	14.03	12.49
	Pr($T > t $)		0.000	0.005	0.003	0.030	0.059

Notes: For each sample, the first two lines report the average WTP of each group, the third line the p -values of two-tailed t -tests for the difference in the WTP between the two groups. ¹ Consumers are classified as 'Higher WTP for sweet oil' in a given round if their average WTP for the two low-polyphenol oils in that round is high than their average WTP for the two high-polyphenol oils in that round, as 'Higher WTP for pungent oil' otherwise. ² Consumers are classified as 'Not liking pungent' if they declared to prefer oils that are 'not bitter/pungent at all' or 'slightly bitter/pungent'; 'Liking pungent', if they declared to prefer oils that are 'bitter/pungent' or 'very bitter/pungent'. ³ Consumers are classified as 'Aware' or 'Unaware' based on their previous knowledge of the relation between bitter/pungent and healthiness. ⁴ Number of observations across all rounds; the number of observations can vary slightly between rounds.

Table 10. WTP across all rounds and in specific rounds for different sub-samples and groups, in Morocco.

Sample	Groups	Obs. ⁴	All stages	Stage 1	Stage 2	Stage 3	Stage 4
All consumers	Low polyphenol oils	1,830	23.84	24.02	23.69	23.32	24.30
	High polyphenol oils	1,833	27.23	24.82	25.43	29.52	29.18
	Pr(T) > t		0.000	0.444	0.045	0.000	0.000
All consumers	Higher WTP for sweet oils ¹	915	24.60	26.20	23.25	20.84	26.93
	Higher WTP for pungent oils ¹	2,748	25.85	23.38	25.17	27.40	26.71
	Pr(T) > t		0.058	0.009	0.041	0.002	0.877
All consumers	National origin (Morocco)	1,832	25.34	24.07	24.42	25.99	26.89
	Local origin (Meknès)	1,831	25.73	24.77	24.71	26.84	26.60
	Pr(T) > t		0.500	0.506	0.732	0.567	0.779
Consumers not liking pungent ²	Low polyphenol oils	1,210	23.43	23.59	23.51	23.03	23.57
	High polyphenol oils	1,213	26.40	23.77	24.35	29.29	28.21
	Pr(T) > t		0.000	0.895	0.417	0.003	0.000
Consumers liking pungent ²	Low polyphenol oils	596	25.12	25.31	24.51	24.34	26.28
	High polyphenol oils	596	29.50	27.44	28.16	30.65	31.76
	Pr(T) > t		0.000	0.194	0.023	0.001	0.004
High polyphenol oils	Consumers not liking pungent ²	1,213	26.40	23.77	24.35	29.29	28.21
	Consumers liking pungent ²	596	29.50	27.44	28.16	30.65	31.76
	Pr(T) > t		0.002	0.031	0.005	0.639	0.036
Low polyphenol oils	Consumers not liking pungent ²	1,210	23.43	23.59	23.51	23.03	23.57
	Consumers liking pungent ²	596	25.12	25.31	24.51	24.34	26.28
	Pr(T) > t		0.015	0.243	0.435	0.325	0.061
Unaware consumers ³	Low polyphenol oils	312	20.97	18.70	21.64	21.79	21.73
	High polyphenol oils	312	23.48	17.67	21.85	28.04	26.34
	Pr(T) > t		0.062	0.522	0.924	0.053	0.158
Aware consumers ³	Low polyphenol oils	1,518	24.42	25.11	24.12	23.63	24.83
	High polyphenol oils	1,521	28.00	26.28	26.17	29.83	29.76
	Pr(T) > t		0.000	0.327	0.029	0.000	0.000
High polyphenol oils	Unaware consumers ³	312	23.48	17.67	21.85	28.04	26.34
	Aware consumers ³	1,521	28.00	26.28	26.17	29.83	29.76
	Pr(T) > t		0.000	0.000	0.010	0.617	0.105
Low polyphenol oils	Unaware consumers ³	312	20.97	18.70	21.64	21.79	21.73
	Aware consumers ³	1,518	24.42	25.11	24.12	23.63	24.83
	Pr(T) > t		0.000	0.000	0.118	0.264	0.086
Higher WTP for pungent oils ¹	Low polyphenol oils	1,373	22.91	21.36	22.92	23.49	23.50
	High polyphenol oils	1,375	28.78	25.40	27.40	31.31	29.91
	Pr(T) > t		0.000	0.003	0.000	0.000	0.000
Higher WTP for sweet oils ¹	Low polyphenol oils	457	26.60	28.55	25.38	22.33	28.35
	High polyphenol oils	458	22.60	23.84	21.14	19.36	25.50
	Pr(T) > t		0.000	0.003	0.005	0.164	0.327

Notes: See Notes to Table 9.